

CASE STUDY

COVID-19 and the education response in Indonesia: exploring the learning crisis

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Version 1

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Acronyms

BOS	Bantuan Operasional Sekolah (school operational assistance)
BPS	Badan Pusat Statistik (Statistics Indonesia)
COVID-19	Novel coronavirus disease 2019
ICT	Information, communication and technology
IT	Information and technology
JB	Jogja Belajar — an online platform created by the Province Education Office of Yogyakarta
LFH	Learning from home
MoE	Ministry of Education and Culture
MoRA	Ministry of Religious Affairs
PJJ	Pembelajaran Jarak Jauh (Distance Learning)
SKB	Surat Keputusan Bersama (Joint Ministerial Decree)

Key messages

- Indonesia's initial response to the COVID-19 pandemic demonstrated a good degree of dynamism and delegation of decision-making on the part of the Ministry of Education and Culture and the Ministry of Religious Affairs
- The crisis has accelerated the implementation of some of the initiatives already planned and aimed at strengthening the use of technology in education.
- The challenges to expand distance learning in Indonesia include: the accessibility and usability of digital platforms; the skill gaps among teaching staff; the struggle to assess and monitor learning outcomes; and the reach of the technology infrastructure in the country.
- Provincial, district, and municipal education authorities can play a more central role in designing, testing and supporting local innovations in offline and online teaching and learning
- To improve online teaching and learning it is critical to strengthen the systems that national and local government have put in place to gather and analyse the feedbacks and suggestions from teachers and students.

Introduction

The education system in Indonesia is managed by the Ministry of Education and Culture (MoE), with the Ministry of Religious Affairs (MoRA) overseeing religious education. Since 1999, Indonesia has been shifting to a decentralised system of government; while the central government MoE and MoRA are responsible for determining national education standards and policies, local governments are responsible for the implementation of education policies and the delivery of education services, including the professional development of education staff and the provision of education facilities. This includes the professional development of education staff and providing cross-district or city facilities for primary and secondary education.

Formal education in Indonesia includes:

- Early childhood (kindergarten) from 4 to 6 years old.
- Primary (or elementary) schools from 7 years old, covering grades 1–6.
- Secondary schools (junior high schools) from 15 years old, covering grades 7–9.
- Tertiary education (high school) from 18 years old (the age limit for entry at grade 10 level is 21 years), covering grades 10–12.¹

The 2019/20 school year started in mid-July 2019, with the first semester going from July to December 2019, the second semester from January to June 2020, and school holidays from 29th June to 11th July 2020.²

Figure 1

COVID-19 cases in Indonesia

Indonesia confirmed its first COVID-19 case on 2nd March 2020. A week later, the World Health Organisation (WHO) declared a global pandemic. At the time of writing, in June 2020, there were 56,385 confirmed COVID-19 cases in Indonesia, and numbers were still rising (Figure 1). In response to the COVID-19 pandemic Indonesia's Minister of Education

1 Peraturan Menteri Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan, Republik Indonesia, Nomor 44, Tahun 2019 (translated: Minister of Education and Culture, Republic of Indonesia, Regulation number 44 of 2019, about admission of new students in kindergarten, primary school, middle school, high school, and middle vocational school).

2 Education calendar, available at: [https://www.quipper.com/id/blog/tips-trick/kalender-
pendidikan-2019-2020](https://www.quipper.com/id/blog/tips-trick/kalender-pendidikan-2019-2020).

and Culture closed 234,233³ elementary schools and lower secondary schools on 17th March 2020, and introduced the learning from home (LFH) policy.^{4,5} Suddenly, 41.98 million⁶ elementary and lower secondary school students had to study from home.

About this case study

In this case study we investigate the learning crisis in Indonesia during COVID-19 pandemic. The aim is to better understand how the LFH policy has been implemented and what technologies were in place or have been put in place to support distance learning.

Figure 2

Location of case study

We collected data in two specific settings in the Province of Yogyakarta:⁷ the city of Yogyakarta, which has 235 elementary and lower secondary schools, and the neighbouring rural areas of the Gunungkidul District, where there are 690 schools.⁸ We selected these

- 3 https://referensi.data.kemdikbud.go.id/index11_sd.php and https://referensi.data.kemdikbud.go.id/index11_smp.php, accessed 24th June 2020.
- 4 <https://www.kemdikbud.go.id/main/blog/2020/03/se-mendikbud-pembelajaran-secara-daring-dan-bekerja-dari-rumah-untuk-mencegah-penyebaran-covid19>.
- 5 <https://sulteng.kemenag.go.id/halaman/detail/surat-edaran-terkait-covid19-coronavirus-disease> (Surat Edaran Ditjen Pendis Nomor 285.1 Tahun 2020 Tentang Upaya Pencegahan Penyebaran Virus COVID-19).
- 6 <https://dapo.dikdasmen.kemdikbud.go.id/> and <http://emispendis.kemenag.go.id/dashboard/index.php>, accessed 27th June 2020.
- 7 Yogyakarta has a Special Region status because historically it was autonomous.
- 8 The elementary and lower secondary schools in Indonesia comprise of general schools under the supervision of the Ministry of Education, and religious-based schools supervised by the Ministry of Religious Affairs.

areas as they are representative of both urban and rural settings, and to leverage existing relationships with local authorities by SurveyMETER.

We conducted 62 semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders — education officials, school principals, teachers and parents. Schools were sampled based on whether they are religious or secular schools, public or private schools, and the distance from the school to the district centre. Data collection was conducted from 5th June to 20th June 2020, by four enumerators.

Education technology before the pandemic and policy response to COVID-19

Before the pandemic, there were still '[...] various degrees of teacher's competency in information, communication and technology (ICT) [...]', (Widodo & Riandi, 2013, cited in Koh et al., 2018).⁹ Data from Statistics Indonesia (BPS) in 2018 shows that only 9% of children aged 13–15, and just 6% of children aged 5–12 years, access the internet.¹⁰ The new Minister of Education and Culture, Nadiem Makarim, is eager to adopt technology and enhance the capability of the education system. He argues that this is a shortcut towards improvement in Indonesian human resources. In November 2020, he asked Google to make Indonesia its first priority for Google new education technology.¹¹ The location of this study, the province of Yogyakarta, is the first province that collaborated with Google For Education in Indonesia.¹² Google For Education supported Jogja Smart Education and activated the Jogja Belajar platform which is owned by Province of Yogyakarta. Gunungkidul District was the location of a pilot project for the implementation of Google For Education.¹³

9 Koh, J.H.L., Chai, C.S., & Natarajan, U. (2018). Developing Indonesia teachers technological pedagogical content knowledge for 21st century learning (TPACK-21CL) through a multi-prong approach. *Journal of International Education and Business*, 3(1), 11–33. Widodo, A., & Riandi. (2013). Dual-mode teacher professional development: Challenges and re-visioning future TPD in Indonesia. *Teacher Development*, 17(3), 380–392.

10 BPS Statistics Indonesia. (2018). *Telecommunication statistics in Indonesia 2019*.

11 <https://tekno.kompas.com/read/2019/11/20/12050047/pesan-mendikbud-nadiem-dan-menkominfo-johnny-untuk-google-indonesia>.

12 <https://jogjaprov.go.id/berita/detail/pemda-diy-launching-google-for-education>.

13 <https://jogja.idntimes.com/news/jogja/daruwaskita/gunungkidul-jadi-pilot-project-google-for-education-di-diy>.

The learning from home policy in Indonesia and Yogyakarta Province

On 15th March 2020, President Joko Widodo announced the steps that Indonesia would take to deal with COVID-19, one of which was an appeal to students to study from home.¹⁴ The decision received political support from the MoE, MoRA, Minister of Health, and Minister of Home Affairs, who jointly provided distance learning guidelines for the new academic year (see also 'Looking ahead').¹⁵ The president changed the budget allocation in several ministries and institutions to deal with the COVID-19 pandemic, doubling the Ministry of Health and MoE budgets and reducing or diverting funds from 20 other ministries.¹⁶

14 <https://kabar24.bisnis.com/read/20200315/15/1213458/ini-pidato-lengkap-presiden-jokowi-soal-penanganan-virus-corona>.

15 <https://bersamahadapikorona.kemdikbud.go.id/panduan-penyelenggaraan-pembelajaran>.

16 <https://www.hukumonline.com/pusatdata/detail/lt5e8c196b78488/node/120/peraturan-presiden-nomor-54-tahun-2020#> and <https://nasional.kompas.com/read/2020/04/13/08351891/selain-pemotongan-jokowi-tambah-anggaran-kemenkes-kemendikbud-dan-belanja?page=all>.

Timeline of policy responses to the COVID-19 pandemic in Indonesia and the Province of Yogyakarta Province 2nd March–15th June 2020

Figure 3
Policy timeline in response to COVID-19 pandemic

Given the education system in Indonesia is decentralised, local authorities have made independent decisions about school closures. For example, in the city of Yogyakarta,

all schools closed on 23rd March 2020.¹⁷ School closure was initially expected to last for a short period but as the number of confirmed COVID-19 cases has continued to increase the LFH policy has been extended five times. And as the risk of transmission COVID-19 remains high¹⁸, secular and religious schools remain closed.

The distance learning guidelines provided by central government offer schools different options, which they can choose from depending on their context and connectivity. The MoE recommends more than 40 online learning applications and platforms — the full list and brief description of which is in [Annex 1](#). The Provincial Education Office in Yogyakarta developed its own platform for online teaching, *Jogja Belajar (Jogja Study)*¹⁹, which covers learning contents in the form of multimedia, audio, radio-streaming, and videos.

These tech platforms have accelerated the distance learning reform that had been launched in December 2019, under the tagline ‘Merdeka Belajar’ (Freedom to Learn). The reform was introduced by Nadiem Anwar Makarim, the then-new Minister of Education and founder of Gojek, the country’s first start-up valued at over \$10 billion. Its primary aim is to reduce the administrative burden of teachers’ workload, offering teachers greater freedom in evaluating student performance and replacing the national exam with minimum competence assessment and behaviour survey.

The MoRA has issued a similar regulation for religious based schools. The guidelines also include provisions for online learning, with platforms [e-learning madrasah](#)²⁰, offline learning TV programmes by the national broadcaster, radio programmes, and printed self-learning material provided by schools.

17 The governor of Yogyakarta issued a policy regarding learning from home, on 19th March 2020, through circular letter number 443/01357 and implemented effectively between 23rd and 31st March 2020.

18 <https://corona.jogjaprovo.go.id/data-statistik>.

19 <https://www.jogjabelajar.org>.

20 <https://elearning.kemenag.go.id/web>.

Key findings

Digital and non-digital technologies

Our interviews show that Google Classroom and G Suite (79%), Rumah Belajar (26%) and Quipper School (16%) are the most popular platforms for distance learning in Yogyakarta Province; use of the Provincial government's own platform, Jogja Belajar, is not widespread. No other platforms or applications were mentioned by respondents. In rural areas, schools and communities have addressed internet connectivity difficulties by a mix of offline and online teaching.

Some schools were using Google Classroom before the pandemic, and they have continued to do so during the school closures. The benefit of Google Classroom is that it provides a virtual study room and doesn't need a special device to use as it can be accessed via mobile phone. Most school principals and teachers interviewed were keen to receive further training to make better use of it. However, this platform is no use when schools, and teachers, and/or learners have no access to internet or limited knowledge of ICT.

Jogja Belajar currently provides limited material. It has not been widely used due to several factors, such as the fact that users need to log in to access the materials and that, once logged in, many have found it hard to find the content they need. Moreover, the platform does not allow for interaction between teachers and students. Instead, the process of learning is considered independent, with teachers preparing test sheets and assignments based on the school curriculum. Some of feedback we received shows that users consider some of the content outdated.

Most of the respondents mentioned that they use WhatsApp as part of distance learning. In most schools, WhatsApp is used to communicate with students and families. In four schools, we found that WhatsApp is used as a learning tool to send and collect assignments. WhatsApp is convenient because almost all parents already have it, and can access the app.

The rural area of the district of Gunungkidul does not have the same internet connectivity as the city of Yogyakarta, and students have more limited access to computers, tablets and smartphones. Schools here adopted a mix of offline and online teaching. In one school, for example, teachers conducted a quick survey at the beginning of lockdown to find out how many learners owned mobile phones or smartphones. The survey we conducted showed that many of the students living in rural areas do not have mobile or smartphones that they could use for online distance learning. Limited signal and internet connections are also a problem in several parts of the district. After discussions with parents, the school organised a once-a-week pick-up of printed teaching materials and assignments, to be returned the following week. Other schools have followed a similar approach to try to reach all of their students.

Respondents also noted that some teachers deliver printed teaching material and assignments to students' homes and, in some cases, schools have allowed students to access and use the school facilities and equipment, if they live nearby.

Other findings from our interviews

The nationwide emergency declared by President Jokowi on 14th March 2020 has allowed a more discretionary use of funds by the MoE. This has led to school operational budgets (BOS) to be used to subsidise online learning needs. Article 9A of Minister Regulation No. 19, states that 2,000 schools can use Regular BOS funds Regular BOS funds to purchase airtime, mobile data and online education services for both educators and students and to support learning from home. The level of budget allocated varies between schools. All the schools that participated in our survey have distributed some level of funding to support home learning. Fourteen schools have provided funds to purchase airtime to both teachers and students. Five schools have provided such funds for teachers alone. Of parents we surveyed, 90% said that the funds they have received is sufficient.

The economic impact of the LFH policy on households

There is mixed evidence about the economic impact of the LFH policy on households. Some respondents have mentioned that distance learning has helped to reduce household expenditure, because parents do not have to provide allowances for food and children do not have to pay for transport — which also applies to teachers who can work from home and no longer need to travel. Other respondents (both parents and teachers) mentioned an increase in overall expenditure due to the increased cost for internet and phone credit, which outweighs the savings on transport.

Distance learning has had a big impact on family expenses, namely to buy airtime. Actually, the school has provided assistance for it, but it's not enough — parents have to spend more. During the learning from home period, the expenses to purchase airtime or mobile data reached Rp 70,000 [approximately USD 4.80] per month. Previously, it was only Rp 20,000 [approximately USD 1.40]. (Parents, Yogyakarta City)

Monitoring learning outcomes

Monitoring learning outcomes has been challenging. Teachers have continued to assess students' progress through the existing systems as mandated by the curriculum. This involves reviewing assignments and observing engagement and communication (for example, through WhatsApp). These assessments have been aggregated into reports. These reports are submitted to school principals, who then report to district education offices and to school supervisors. Monitoring is conducted via completion of online questionnaires by parents, or weekly online meetings with teachers to discuss challenges and issues with distance learning.

Teachers reported that, in distance learning, it is difficult to know whether the student is focused and understands what the teacher is teaching, and it is difficult to be sure whether students are following the lessons. Moreover, some teachers feel that they are struggling to involve students who do not have access to the internet and online platforms. Printed material helps, but is not a substitute for an online class. The monitoring information is used by the district offices of MoE and MoRA and by schools to support teachers and parents who have difficulty accessing the necessary learning technology or experience other LFH challenges.

Looking ahead: government plans

The recent announcement indicates that the country will allow phased reopening of schools located in COVID-19 unaffected areas, or 'green zones'. As reported cases of COVID-19 are still high in Indonesia, the MoE, MoRA, Ministry of Home Affairs, and Ministry of Health agreed to release a joint decision on 15th June 2020 on 'Guidelines for Learning Activities in New School/Academic Year during COVID-19 Pandemic'. This decision stipulates that only schools in unaffected areas or green zones (6% cities/districts) are allowed to open schools for the new school year in July 2020. Schools in low-risk areas ('yellow zones'), medium risk areas ('orange zones'), and high-risk areas ('red zones'), (94% of cities/districts across the country) must still continue distance learning activities.

The previous two guidelines on learning from home, issued by MoE and MoRA on 18th May 2020, will continue to be adopted by schools. Under the MoE guidelines, the government is expecting to meet students' right to education during the pandemic, as well as ensuring psychological support for teachers, students and parents during what is a difficult time. The guidelines provide specific details for school principals in relation to students with disabilities. It also includes ways to coordinate teachers to make use of and adapt teaching materials for students with disabilities. It explains the distribution of offline learning facilities and teaching aids to students' homes, including educational aids for students with disabilities (for those who do not have access to online learning).

The guidelines also contain referral information that can be accessed by the principals if psychosocial support for teachers, parents or guardians, and students is required. They also provide guidance on what teachers should do pre-learning, during learning and post-learning when students learn offline and through television and radio.

For faith-based schools, MoRA guidelines emphasise the notion that learning from home does not have to meet the demands of competence in the curriculum, but rather to the development of soft skills such as independence, and other social empathy.

Conclusions and suggestions

Indonesia's initial response to the COVID-19 pandemic demonstrated a good degree of dynamism and delegation of decision-making on the part of the MoE and the MoRA. Both ministries have issued detailed guidelines to implement the LFH policies, with a number of suggestions both in terms of online and offline teaching, which district authorities and schools have adapted to their specific contexts.

The crisis has accelerated the implementation of some of the already planned activities to strengthen the use of technology in education. Overall, less than 10% of the 40+ digital platforms are being used during the lockdown.

As we write this, at the end of June 2020, only a small number of schools, will re-open in mid-July for the new school year. Many more schools will continue to face the same challenges to distance learning, including the accessibility and usability of the platforms, skill gaps among teaching staff, challenges in monitoring outcomes and limitations in technology infrastructure.

To overcome some of these interrelated problems, we suggest:

- Improving the process of learning from home and its output by adopting the MoE and MoRA guidelines on distance learning during COVID-19.
- Providing space, support and training to teachers so that they can improve their teaching creativity, and providing teaching materials tailored to the available facilities and infrastructure and to the situation of the learners and their families.
- Increasing support to help teachers improve their ICT skills, through direct virtual learning and providing opportunities for mutual learning between teachers in schools and outside of school.
- Provincial, district, or municipal offices of the MoE and MoRA have to play a more direct role in facilitating online and offline learning, as mandated in the national guidelines.
- Central and local government need to facilitate the improvement of online platforms, informed by feedback from users — both teachers and students.
- Improve ICT facilities and infrastructure in areas that currently have poor network connectivity to increase the access of online learning.

Annexes

Annex 1: List of apps and platforms

Below, a list of the platforms recommended by the Ministry of Education and Culture, the Ministry of Religious Affairs, and the Education Department of the Province of Yogyakarta:

1. [Rumah Belajar \(Learning House\)](#) of the Pusdatin (Data and Information Centre), Ministry of Education and Culture, an alternative to learning resources by using digital technology. Available features are learning resources, virtual laboratory, digital class, electronic books, literature, for example. Contents and features are available for free.
2. [Education TV](#), Ministry of Education and Culture, a dedicated TV station for broadcasting learning and education material, accessible for free using satellite disc or relays station.
3. [Digital Learning of Pusdatin \(Data and Information Center\)](#), and [SEAMOLEC](#), Ministry of Education and Culture, a platform equipped with various digital contents related to education and culture, accessible for free online.
4. [Face-to-face online](#), greeting program of the ambassadors of Rumah Belajar, Pusdatin (Data and Information Centre), online meeting provided by Webex Cisco, Ministry of Education and Culture.
5. [LMS SIAJAR from SEAMOLEC](#), Ministry of Education and Culture, a learning management system application for distance learning for high schools, the system includes tools for designing, implementing and evaluating learning activities.
6. [Online application for A,B,C package](#), a learning management system application for distance learning for equality education, the system includes tools for designing, implementing and evaluating learning activities.
7. [Guru berbagi \(Teacher sharing\)](#), a dedicated website for teachers, government, community and education enthusiasts to share and discuss learning material and practices.
8. [Digital reading](#), a web-based digital reading platform.
9. [Learning video](#), a video-on-demand portal for education and learning materials.
10. [Suara edukasi \(education voice\)](#), Ministry of Education and Culture, a radio channel for education (AM 1440 Khz).
11. [Radio edukasi \(education radio\)](#), Ministry of Education and Culture, a radio channel for education.
12. [Sahabat keluarga \(family bestfriend\)](#), a website containing information sources and teaching materials for parenting and family education.
13. [Ruang guru PAUD \(early childhood education\)](#), Ministry of Education and Culture, a website portal dedicated for early child education teachers, providing learning and education sources and materials.
14. [Electronic school book](#), school text books to download for free.
15. [Mobile education](#), multimedia teaching material, digital mobile content application for education.
16. [Equality Education Module](#), text books to download for free for equality education.
17. [Elementary, junior, high and vocational school student](#), teaching material downloadable for free.
18. [Online course for teachers SEAMOLEC](#), e-learning platform that facilitates massive online open courses; open educational resources are also available.
19. [Online class for students and university student](#).

20. Institution Repository, Ministry of Education and Culture.
21. [Online journal](#), Ministry of Education and Culture.
22. [Digital book open-access](#).
23. [EPERPUSDIKBUD \(Google Play\)](#), e-library application.

Other sources managed by education technology providers and partners:

24. [Sekretariat Nasional Satuan Pendidikan Aman Bencana \(SPAN\)](#), learning materials and resources for teachers and students are provided by UNICEF and members of education clusters: Save The Children, Plan International Indonesia, Wahana Visi Indonesia, Kerlip, Predikt, LPBNU, Muhammadiyah, Asia Foundation, Kompak, Inovasi/TASS, Tanoto Foundation, KYPA, and Caritas Indonesia, who are forming this national secretariat for disaster-safe education.
25. [WeKiddo](#) is a mobile application that connects schools, parents and children to enhance parent's contribution to children development and future. WeKiddo support learning from home by facilitating better communication between schools, teachers, parents and students. Application and features are free.
26. [XL Axiata](#), telecommunication provider, offers free access to online learning portals, government websites, Microsoft Office 365 and other education institutes (terms and conditions apply).
27. [Indosat Ooredoo](#), a telecommunication provider, offers free access to online learning portals (RuangGuru, Quipper, Sekolahmu.com and Rumah Belajar) and university portals (terms and conditions apply).
28. [Telkomsel](#), a telecommunication provider, offers free access to Quipper, Zenius, Bahaso, Sekolah.mu, and some e-learning campuses (terms and conditions apply).
29. [Pahamify](#) is an education technology company and developer learning application in Indonesia, containing videos of animated learning activities, including quizzes.
30. [MejaKita](#) is an online education platform that empowers students across Indonesia to collaborate in education. MejaKita promotes theme-based learning and discussion. This platform has been used by approximately 15,000 students in 223 cities.
31. [ICANDO](#) is a learning application for children. The application is developed based on Curriculum 2013, enhanced with mini games to motivate fun learning.
32. [IndonesiaX](#), launched in 2015, IndonesiaX has been offering high-quality courses for free. Courses are delivered by qualified tutors and instructors.
33. [Ganeca Digital](#) is an online learning application that offers hundreds of K13 books for students and teachers. Application and features are available for free (terms and conditions apply).
34. [Google for Education](#), Google is committed to improve learning for everyone. G-Suite for education, which includes Google Meet and Google Classroom, is available for free to help schools, teachers and students to stay connected and learning effectively while distanced.
35. [Kelas Pintar](#) is a digital education provider that offers students and teachers with personalised dashboard and interactive contents, Kelas Pintar is also available in India, Singapore, South Africa and UAE.
36. [Microsoft Office 365](#) is offered to teachers and students for free. Available features include Microsoft Word, Excel, Powerpoint, One Note and Teams. To access this for free, teachers and students must provide a valid email address.

37. Quipper School offers innovative method for learning, allowing teachers to manage job and homework effectively and help them to identify students' strengths and weaknesses.
38. Ruangguru is a technology-based online education service; it offers virtual classes, online tests, video subscription, marketplace, private courses, and so on. During the COVID-19 pandemic, Ruangguru offers free online class (terms and conditions apply).
39. SekolahMu is a technology and collaboration platform that offers a blended learning program. SekolahMu is an education collaboration hub of hundreds of schools and selected institutions who provide learning materials required.
40. Zenius offers thousands selection of learning videos from elementary school to high school level, including examples of national test. Zenius also provides exercise test to enrol to prestigious universities in Indonesia.
41. Cisco Webex is an online collaboration platform offering virtual classroom-like meetings. Webex allows teachers and students to share, interact and collaborate virtually through a computer/smartphone screen. Teachers and students can also hold discussions through the available group chat room feature.
42. Jogja Belajar (Jogja Study), a platform owned by Provincial Education Office in Yogyakarta. Learning contents in the form of multimedia, audio, radio-streaming, videos.
43. E-learning madrasah, a platform.

Annex 2: Timeline of the policy response to COVID-19 at different administrative levels in Indonesia: national, Yogyakarta Province, Yogyakarta City, and Gunungkidul District (1st February–15th June 2020)

Part 1 of 12

📅 1st February 2020 (national level)	The Indonesian government repatriated 243 Indonesian citizens from the province of Hubei in China (the capital is Wuhan). 238 of them were evacuated for quarantine to the Riau Islands where they arrived on 2nd February 2020.
📅 2nd March 2020 (national level)	President Joko Widodo announced the first case of COVID-19 virus in Indonesia. The first case were two Indonesian citizens who had been in contact with a group of Japanese people who had come to Indonesia.
📅 3rd March 2020 (Yogyakarta Province level)	<i>Yogyakarta governor's instruction number 2/NSTR/2020 concerning increased awareness of the risk of coronavirus disease transmission (COVID-19) infection.</i> The Regional Secretary, Paniradya Patil DPRD Secretary, Head of Regional Service/Head of Satpol PP/Head of Regional Sadan/Head of Sadan Regional Liaison/Head of bureau/UPT, and Director of SUMO in Yogyakarta begin to implement the following activities in in Yogyakarta with the following tasks: internal and external coordination of each work unit to map targets with potential transmission of COVID-19; socialisation in controlling risk transmission of COVID-19 (epidemiologic monitoring and investigation); efforts to create a conducive atmosphere in the community; and increase community awareness and participation in controlling the risk of COVID-19 transmission.
📅 9th March 2020 (national level)	<i>Circular letter N.2/2020 regarding the preventions and handling of COVID-19 issues by the MoE.</i> In connection with the spread of coronavirus disease (COVID-19), the minister of education and culture calls on the head of the main unit and the head of the technical implementing unit to take preventative and countermeasures, such as ensuring the availability of facilities for handwashing with Soap (CTPS), disposable cleaning tools (tissue), and/or hand sanitisers in strategic locations in the work unit environment; ensure work units conduct routine room and environmental cleaning, limit official travel abroad and suspend overseas travel for purposes that can be delayed, especially to countries affected by COVID-19. This circular letter also provides prevention of the virus transmission based on the level of risk of transmission (attachment).
📅 9th March 2020 (national level)	<i>Circular letter N.3/2020 concerning the preventions of COVID-19 on education units.</i> The circular letter is addressed to: Head of Provincial Education Office, Head of District Education Office, Head of Higher Education Institution, Head of Higher Education, Principal in all areas in Indonesia. In order to prevent the development and spread of coronavirus disease (COVID-19) within the education unit environment, the Minister of Education appeal education units in the region to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Optimise the role of Usaha Kesehatan Sekolah (UKS) or health service units by coordinating with local health facilities. - Monitor attendance of education unit personnel; give permission to the people who are sick not to come to the education unit. - Does not impose penalties/sanctions for those who do not come due to sick, and does not enforce an incentive-based presence policy. - Report to the District Health Office, the District Education Office and/or Higher Education Institutions if there is a large number of absences due to illness related to breathing.

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📅 14th March 2020 (national level)

Circular letter number 285.1 of 2020 concerning efforts to prevent the spread of the COVID-19 signed by the Director General of Islamic Education on 14th March, 2020.

In the context of preventing the spread of the COVID-19, several things were addressed: the implementation of teaching and learning activities and examinations in Madrasa and Islamic boarding schools to adjust to local government policies; prepare the learning materials to anticipate the learning needs of Madrasa students who are in areas that are closed by the local government; the computer-based National Examination for Madrasas located in the area which is closed will be served specifically after the holiday period ends; the implementation of the national examination follows the Ministry of Education and Culture's policies; students/santri of boarding schools/ma'had/Islamic boarding schools are suggested not to go out of their boarding schools/ma'had/Islamic boarding schools or not to be visited by parents/guardians first. For boarding-based Madrasas to take steps to prevent the spread of COVID-19 by educating students/santri to wash their hands with soap, clean the dormitory environment, roll up the mosque carpet, and follow protocols established by the government; and so on.

📅 16th March 2020 (national level)

Circular letter of the Minister of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform number 19 year 2020 dated 16th March 2020 regarding the adjustment of the work system of civil servants in preventing the transmission of COVID-19 within government agencies.

The letter was addressed to the ministers of Indonesia Maju Cabinet, Cabinet Secretary, Commander of the Indonesian National Armed Forces, Chief of the Indonesian National Police, General Attorney of the Republic of Indonesia, Head of the Indonesian State Intelligence Agency, Heads of Non-Ministry Government Institutions, Head of Secretariat of State Institutions, Head of Secretariat of Non-structural Institutions, Head of Public Broadcasting Institution, Governors, Regents, and Mayors.

This letter was issued considering the increasing spread of COVID-19 in Indonesian and WHO's official statement about COVID-19 as a global pandemic, the Indonesian President's statement on the spreading of COVID-19 as a national disaster (non-natural disaster), and direction from the president to develop a policy that allows some civil servants to work from home.

This letter contains the implementation of official duties by work from home for the civil servants as an effort to prevent the spread of COVID-19 within the government agency.

📅 16th March 2020 (national level)

In his speech on Monday 16th March 2020, the Indonesian Minister of Education and Culture said: 'I still see a lot of people who are actually able to work from home, still doing activities outside. For this reason, I emphasise a number of things; First, coronavirus is not a virus that can be underestimated, this is a dangerous virus with a very fast transmission rate. Second, even though we have no symptoms, but we can be carriers and transmit it to people with poor health conditions such as elderly, or people with diabetes, hypertension, and other health conditions. So remember, every time we go out, we can threaten the lives of others'. In his speech, the minister also invited all people to show that Indonesia is a country with mutual cooperation principles. Let save the lives of Indonesian by working from home, learning from home, and worshipping from home.

📅 16th March 2020 (other actors)

Circular letter Number 53 of 2020 concerning Sunan Kalijaga Yogyakarta UIN Policy issued on 14/2/2020 and valid from 16th March 2020–30th April 2020.

In the official circular letter published on 16th March 2020, the Rector of Gadjah Mada University (UGM) in Yogyakarta, Prof. Panut Mulyono, stated that the campus was in standby status with regard to COVID-19. UGM has changed the teaching and learning activities on campus and classrooms to online learning (Number 1604 /UN1.P/HKL TR/2020).

Private campuses in Yogyakarta also apply the same thing.

📅 17th March 2020 (national level)

Circular letter of the Minister of Home Affairs number 440/2436/SJ dated 17th March 2020, concerning prevention of the transmission of coronavirus disease (COVID-19) in the regional government areas.

Local government administrators (Regional Heads and DPRD), and the civil servants (ASN) can carry out official duties by work from home.

🏠 17th March 2020 (national level)

Circular letter of the Minister of Education and Culture number 36962/MPK.A /HK/2020, 17th March 2020: Online learning and work from home to prevent the spread of COVID-19.

Various providers have collaborated with the Ministry of Education and Culture to provide online learning facilities for free: Rumah Belajar, Google G Suites for Education, Kelas Pntar, Quiper School, Sekolah online Ruang Guru, Sekolahmu, Zeus.

The government reported the latest data regarding patients infected with COVID-19 on Tuesday, 17th March, 2020. The number of patients increased to 172. This number has increased from 38 cases on Monday, 134 cases on 16th March. The number of death due to this virus does not increase significantly (increase 5 deaths) and 9 patients were declared cured.

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🏠 17th March 2020 (Yogyakarta Province level)

Circular letter of Yogyakarta governor number 433/4956 dated 17th March 2020 concerning Adjustment of the ASN Work System to prevent the spread of COVID-19 in Yogyakarta.

Regent/Mayor and the Head of Regional Apparatus instruct to make efforts to prevent COVID-19 through cleaning or sanitising the work environment.

All ASNs continue to carry out their duties in their respective offices as usual unless stated as ODP (person under monitoring).

For activities that invite and gather many people to be postponed until 31st March 2020 and evaluated as needed except the most important and cannot be postponed activities.

Travel abroad, outside the region or within the region are postponed until further evaluation unless the activities are very important and cannot be postponed.

For ASNs who have travelled to infected areas within the country or abroad, or have interacted with ODP and Patients Under Supervision (PDP) within the last 14 days, please immediately come to the health facility or contact the Call Center (0274) 555585 and 08112764800.

The Regent/Mayor, Head of Vertical Institution and Head of Regional Apparatus always monitor this circular letter.

🏠 18th March 2020 (Yogyakarta Province level)

Circular letter of the Ministry of Religious Affairs, Yogyakarta Office, number B-1006/Kw.12.1/4/HM.01/03/2020.

To: Head of District/City Religious Affairs Office in Yogyakarta.

Subject: Arrangement of ASN Work Schedule and System under Yogyakarta Regional Office of Ministry of Religious Affairs in Preventing the Spread of COVID-19.

In an effort to prevent and minimise the spread and reduce the risk of COVID-19 within the Ministry of Religious Affairs Office in Yogyakarta in particular and the wider community in general and ensuring the implementation of the duties, functions, and implementation of public services to continue to run effectively.

Valid until 18th–31st March 2020.

🏠 19th March 2020 (Yogyakarta Province level)

Circular letter of Yogyakarta Governor number 443/01357 dated 19th March 2020 concerning anticipation of the spread of coronavirus infection (COVID-19) in the special region of Yogyakarta.

Stop all activities of students at school and applied learn from home policy from 23rd March–31st March 2020.

 20th March 2020 (Yogyakarta Province level)

Circular letter of Minister of Education, Youth, and Sports number 421/02280 regarding distance learning for school children to prevent COVID-19, imposed 16 provisions for regulating activities in the educational environment, among others, eliminating all student activities at school and replaced with learning from home applies to all elementary school — high school levels and the equivalent. The national examination of 2019/2020 will be implemented.

Addressed to the Head of Yogyakarta Regional Office of the Ministry of Religious Affairs, Head of District/City Education Office in Yogyakarta, Head of District/City Dikmen Education Office in Yogyakarta, High School/Vocational High School Principals in Yogyakarta. By considering the spread of COVID-19 which was declared a pandemic by WHO and in the context of preventing further spread in the environment of educational units in Yogyakarta region; circular letter of the Minister of Health number PK.02.02/BV1/839/2020 concerning efforts to prevent transmission of COVID-19 at the workplace; circular letter of the Minister of Education and Culture number 3 of 2020 concerning prevention of COVID-19 in the education unit; instruction of Yogyakarta Governor number 2/INSTR/2020 dated 3rd March 2020 concerning increased awareness of the risk of COVID-19 transmission; Yogyakarta governor circular letter number 443/01357 dated 19th March 2020 concerning anticipation of the spread of COVID-19 in the educational environment in Yogyakarta. It requires regulation in the educational environment, eliminating all student activities at school and replaces them with learning from home starting from 23rd March until 31st March 2020, for pre-school — senior high school and the equivalent as well as SLB students who are not currently taking the national examination (UN). The national examination of 2019/2020 will be carried out according to the schedule determined by the standard operational procedure of national examination.

 20th March 2020 (Yogyakarta Province level)

Yogyakarta governor decree number 65/KEP/2020 dated 20th March 2020 concerning determination of coronavirus disease emergency response status (COVID-19) in the special region of Yogyakarta.

Yogyakarta governor considers that based on a proposal from the Head of the Implementing Agency of BNPB Yogyakarta number 360/01077 dated 17th March 2020, it is necessary to stipulate the governor decree regarding determination of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) emergency response status in Yogyakarta.

Decided: 1) Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) response status in Yogyakarta, starting from 20th March 2020 until 29th May 2020. 2) The emergency response status can be extended in accordance with the conditions. 3) Assign the Deputy Governor of Yogyakarta to take actions needed to prevent and deal with the adverse effects, including rescue activities, and recovery of victims of COVID-19 in Yogyakarta.

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 20th March 2020 (Yogyakarta Province level)

Circular letter of Yogyakarta Education Office number 421/02280 dated 20th March 2020 regarding distance learning/learning at home for school children in the context of COVID-19 prevention, addressed to the Head of the Yogyakarta Regional Office of the Ministry of Religious Affairs, Head of District/City Education Office in Yogyakarta, Head of District/City Dikmen Education Office in Yogyakarta, Head of High School/Vocational High School in Yogyakarta. By considering the spread of COVID-19 which was declared a pandemic by WHO and in the context of preventing further spread in the environment of educational units in Yogyakarta region; circular letter of the Minister of Health number PK.02.02/BV1/839/2020 concerning efforts to prevent transmission of COVID-19 at the workplace; circular letter of the Minister of Education and Culture of number 3 of 2020 concerning prevention of COVID-19 in the education unit; instruction of Yogyakarta Governor number 2/INSTR/2020 dated 3rd March 2020 concerning increased awareness of the risk of COVID-19 transmission; Yogyakarta Governor circular letter number 443/01357 dated 19th March 2020 concerning anticipation of the spread of COVID-19 infection in the educational environment in Yogyakarta. It requires regulation in the educational environment, eliminating all student activities at school and replaces them with learning from home starting from 23rd March until 31st March 2020, for pre-school — senior high school and the equivalent as well as SLB students who are not currently taking the national examination (UN). The national examination of 2019/2020 will be carried out according to the schedule determined by the standard operational procedure of national examination.

In implementing distance learning models (online), teachers can optimise the virtual class 'Jogja Belajar Class' developed by the Educational Communication Technology Center (BTKP) of the DIKPORA DIY, with the address jogjabelajar.org, Rumah Belajar developed by the Data and Information Center (Pusdatin) Ministry of Education and Culture with the address belajar.kemendikbud.go.id, utilising information technology and other social media that is possible and affordable.

 20th March 2020 (Yogyakarta City and Gunungkidul District)

Circular letter of Yogyakarta Mayor number 443/952/SE/2020 concerning anticipation of the spread of coronavirus diseases (COVID-19) in education unit in Yogyakarta City. This letter refers to the circular letter of Yogyakarta Governor number 443/01357/202.

Determine: The national examination will be conducted by the Ministry of Education and Culture, School Exams for SD/MI in the city will continue to be implemented. Stop all student activities at school and replace them with learning from home from 23th March–31st March, 2020, 4th March, 2020.

 24th March 2020 (Yogyakarta Province level)

Curricular letter of the Minister of Education and Culture number 4 2020 on the implementation of education policy in the emergency period of coronavirus disease (COVID-19).

Concerning the increasing spread of the COVID-19, the 2020 national examination is canceled, apply learning from home, the education office and schools were asked to prepare PPDB or new students enrollment that follows the health protocol to prevent the spread of COVID-19, the school operational assistance fund/BOP can be utilised for the prevention of COVID-19.

This circular letter is addressed to the governor, regents/mayors throughout Indonesia.

 24th March 2020 (Yogyakarta Province level)

Changes in ASN Work Schedule and Arrangement under the Yogyakarta Regional Office of the Ministry of Religious Affairs in the context of preventing the spread of COVID-19.

Addressed to the Head of Administration Section, Head of Division, Counsellor, Head of District/City of the Ministry of Religious Affairs, Head of Madrasah, Head of KUA in the Yogyakarta Regional Office of the Ministry of Religious Affairs.

Following our Letter Number: B- 1006/Kw.12.1/4/HM.01/03/2020 dated 18th March 2020 concerning arrangement of ASN work schedule and system under the Yogyakarta Regional Office of the Ministry of Religious Affairs in the context of preventing the spread of COVID-19, and considering the circular letter of the Minister of Religious Affairs Number 04 of 2020 concerning amendment to circular letter number 03 of 2020 concerning adjustment of work systems in the effort to prevent the spread of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) to the Ministry of Religious Affairs, and ensure the implementation of the duties, functions and implementation of public services to run effectively then all employees in the Yogyakarta Regional Office of the Ministry of Religious Affairs, including high level management officers, administrators, supervisors, JFT, implementers or other employees *have to work at home and complete their respective functional duties.*

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 24th March 2020 (Yogyakarta Province level)

Circular letter number 800/5316 dated 24th March 2020, concerning the adjustment of the work system in COVID-19 emergency response status in Yogyakarta.

Addressed to Regents/Mayors throughout Yogyakarta, Head of Vertical Institution, Head of Regional Apparatus.

Work system regulation, first, the representation of employees whose tasks are in regional government agencies/work units is regulated by at least 50% work from offices and 50% work from home. Second, the head of the agency regulates the distribution of employee attendance at their respective agencies with consideration of structural officials' concerns, employees using public transportation, office distance from the residence more than 40 km, and employee health and family health status of ODP/PDP/COVID-19 positive. Arrange the work system not to interfere with the government and services to the community.

 24th March 2020 (Yogyakarta Province level)

Circular letter of Yogyakarta Regional office of Ministry of Religious Affairs number B-1064/Kw.12.1/4/HM.01/03/2020 concerning changes in arrangement of ASN Work Schedule and System under Yogyakarta Regional Office of Ministry of Religious Affairs in Preventing the spread of COVID-19.

All employees in the Yogyakarta Regional office of Ministry of Religious Affairs, including high level of management officers, administrators, supervisors, JFTs, implementers or other employees *must work from home to complete their respective functional assignments valid until 31st March 2020.*

 24th March 2020 (Yogyakarta City and Gunungkidul District)

Circular letter of Gunungkidul District Office of Education number: 421/2210/MP-1 concerning the extension of the period of learning from home (BDR) during the COVID-19 pandemic and holidays for Eid 1441H and other holidays.

- a. For education units implementing 5 (five) school days of learning, starting on 29th April 2020 until 15th May 2020.
- b. For education units implementing 6 (six) school days of learning, starting 29th April 2020 until 16th May 2020.

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 26th March 2020 (national level)

Circular letter of the Minister of Religious Affairs number B-1069/Kw.12.2/1/PP.00/03/2020 dated March 26 2020 concerning education policy in Madrasah in the emergency prevention of COVID-19.

This letter is addressed to the Head of the District/City Office of the Ministry of Religious Affairs, C.q. Head of District/City Madrasah Education Section in Yogyakarta.

Following up the spread and further prevention of coronavirus disease (COVID-19) in the educational unit environment in Yogyakarta, and consider:

1. Circular letter of the Minister of Education and Culture number: 4 of 2020 concerning the implementation of education policy in the emergency period of coronavirus disease (COVID-19).
2. Decree of Yogyakarta Governor number: 65/Kep/2020 concerning determination of the emergency response status of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) Yogyakarta.
3. Circular letter of Yogyakarta Governor number: 443/01357 dated 19th March, 2020 concerning anticipation of the spread of coronavirus disease infection (COVID-19) in the educational environment in Yogyakarta.
4. Circular letter of Yogyakarta Governor number: 443/5425 dated 26th March, 2020, regarding the implementation of emergency education policy in the transmission of coronavirus disease (COVID-19) in the educational environment in Yogyakarta.
5. Letter of the Director of the KSKK Madrasah of Directorate General of Islamic Education of Minister of Religious Affairs number B-686.1/DJ.I/Dt.II/PP.00/03/2020, dated 24th March 2020 concerning the learning mechanism and evaluation of Madrasahs in emergency prevention of COVID-19.
6. Circular letter of the Head of the Yogyakarta Regional Office of the Ministry of Religious Affairs number B-1064/Kw.12.1/4/HM.01/03/2020 dated 24th March 2020 concerning the amendment to the arrangement of the ASN Work Schedule and Work System under the Yogyakarta Regional Office of the Ministry of Religious Affairs in preventing the spread of COVID-19.
7. Circular letter of the Head of the Department of Education, Youth and Sports Yogyakarta number: 421/02391 dated 26th March 2020 concerning the implementation of education policy in during the spread of COVID-19.

Notifying that:

- a. National examination (UN) for MTs and MA TP 2019/2020 is cancelled.
- b. Madrasah Aliyah (MA) and Madrasah Tsanawiyah (MTs) who have implemented the UAMBN, the examinees will get a UAMBN result certificate (SHUAMBN). Madrasah Tsanawiyah (MTs) that have not yet implemented the UAMBN, the implementation of the UAMBN is cancelled.
- c. SD/MI 2019/2020 Exams conducted by the Yogyakarta Youth and Sports Education Agency with the District/City Education Office and the Yogyakarta Regional Office of the Ministry of Religious Affairs in order to facilitate the Working Group of SD/MI, SDLB teachers in Yogyakarta were cancelled.

The learning from home is carried out with the following conditions (among them) before extending distance learning/online learning, the education unit evaluates the effectiveness, student learning burden, and success of distance learning/online learning; learning activities and assignments during learning from home can vary between students, for example.

📅 26th March 2020 (Yogyakarta Province level)	Circular letter of Yogyakarta Governor regarding COVID-19 emergency disaster response dated 26th March 2020 at https://www.jogjaprov.go.id/peng-Announcement/detail/100-surat-edaran-gubern-diy-mengenai-tanggap-darurat-bencana-covid-19 .
📅 27th March 2020 (national level)	<p>Decree of the Director General of Islamic Education number 1801 of 2020 concerning amendment to the decree of the Director General of Islamic Education number 7330 of 2019 regarding technical guidelines for the management of educational operational assistance — Raudatul Athfal and school operational assistance for Madrasahs in the 2020 fiscal year.</p> <p>In this decree, it is explained that in addition to the scope of the BOP RA and BOS Madrasah financing components, in the context of preventing the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic, BOP and BOS can be used to finance activities including: purchase/rent of facilities/equipment or implementation of activities needed to prevent COVID-19, purchase/rent of facilities/equipment/to support the continuity of the teaching-learning process.</p>
📅 27th March 2020 (national level)	<p>Circular letter of the Minister of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia number: B-699/DT.I.I/PP.03/03/2020 regarding the use of education operational assistance — Raudatul Athfal (BOP-RA) and school operational assistance (BOS) to Madrasahs in preventing the spread of COVID-19 in Raudatul Athfal and Madrasah environments.</p> <p>This circular letter stated that the use of Madrasah BOP-RA and BOS funds in addition to those stipulated in the decree of the Director General of Islamic Education number 7330 of 2019 concerning technical guidelines for managing BOP-RA and BOS Madrasah funds for the 2020 fiscal year, during the emergency period to prevent the spread of the COVID-19, can be used to purchase/rent of facilities/equipment or carry out activities needed to prevent COVID-19, purchase/rent of facilities/equipment to support the continuity of the teaching and learning process both at the madrasahs and at home, implementation of other activities that support efforts to prevent the spread of COVID-19 in RA and Madrasah environments.</p>
📅 30th March 2020 (national level)	<p>Circular letter of the Minister of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform number 34 of 2020 dated 30th March 2020 concerning amendment to the circular letter number 19 of 2020 concerning adjustment of the ASNPNB Work System number 13.A of 2020 concerning the extension of the emergency situation in the coronavirus disaster in Indonesia.</p> <p>Deciding the extension of the period of work from home. The work from home period based on the circular letter number 19 of 2020 concerning the adjustment of the ASN work system in preventing the spread of COVID-19 within the government agencies is extended to 21st April 2020, and will be further evaluated as needed.</p>
📅 30th March 2020 (national level)	<p>Circular letter of the Minister of Religious Affairs number SE. 5 of 2020 dated 30th March 2020 concerning adjustment of Work Systems in preventing the spread of COVID-19 at the Ministry of Religious Affairs work units.</p> <p>Concerning the increasing spread of COVID-19 and new policies related to the synergy of the spread of the virus, as well as efforts to carry out physical distancing and prioritising health and safety of employees of the Ministry of Religious Affairs, need to adjust the preparation of employee work systems based on the provisions of attendance arrangements at the office, work from home arrangements, and so on.</p>
📅 30th March 2020 (Yogyakarta City and Gunungkidul District)	<p>Circular letter of Yogyakarta Governor of number 421/5598 concerning extension of distance/online learning period for students in the emergency period of the spread of COVID-19 in the educational environment at Yogyakarta.</p> <p>Extension of distance learning period for students throughout Yogyakarta from 1st–14th April 2020.</p>

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 30th March 2020 (Yogyakarta City and Gunungkidul District)

Circular letter number 421/1924/Um The Education District & Youth and Sports District Office of Gunungkidul regarding the extension of the implementation of learning from home (Bdr) during the COVID-19 pandemic. The letter is addressed to the Head of Kindergarten (Tk/Ra), Principal of Elementary Schools (Sd/Mi), Principal of Junior High Schools (Smp/Mts), Heads of all non-formal education units In Gunungkidul District.

Following up the transmission and further prevention of coronavirus disease (COVID-19) in the environment of education units in Gunungkidul:

1. Circular letter of the Minister of Education number 4 of 2020 concerning the implementation of Education Education Policy in the Emergency of coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic.
2. Circular letter of the Governor of Yogyakarta number 421/5598 concerning the extension of distance/online learning program for students during the emergency of COVID-19 pandemic in the educational environment in Yogyakarta.

Needs rearrangement of educational activities within the education unit environment as follows:

1. All PAUD, TK/RA, and non-formal PAUD education units halted activities from 1st through 14th April 2020.
2. Extend the period of online learning activities (BDR) online or manually using the materials and assignments given by the teacher to SD/MI and SMP/MTS, and temporarily stop the teaching-learning activities.
3. Package A, package B, and package C programs, as well as LKP in Gunungkidul Districts is halted from 1st to 14th April 2020.
4. The implementation of online teaching and learning activities and the assignments for the students must be provided proportionally and should not burden the students.
5. Each education unit must update the latest information about the transmission of coronavirus disease (COVID-19) to decide the preventive measures related to teaching and learning activities and maintain the quality of education in Gunungkidul.
6. This circular letter is valid until 14th April 2020 and will be evaluated further in accordance with the current situation and conditions.

 1st April 2020 (Yogyakarta Province level)

Circular letter of Yogyakarta regional office of the Ministry of Religious Affairs number B-1096/Kw.12.2/1/PP.00/03/2020 concerning education policy in Madrasah during the emergency period of COVID-19 pandemic.

Extend distance learning period for Mprimary school/MI, junior high school/MTs, senior high school/MA/MAK students in Yogyakarta from 1st–21st April 2020.

 13th April 2020 (national level)

The Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia number 19 year 2020 concerning amendment to regulation of the Minister of Education and culture Number 8 year 2020 concerning technical guidelines for regular school assistance. Issued on 9th April 2020 and enacted on 13th April 2020.

One of government's efforts in supporting the implementation of learning from home program due to the increasing cases of coronavirus disease (COVID-19) transmission in education units is to change the school operational financing policy through regular school operational assistance funds which is regulated in Minister of Education and Culture Regulation number 8 year 2020 concerning technical guidelines for regular school operational assistance.

During the statement of public health emergency of COVID-19 status by the central government, all schools can use regular BOS funds to finance the services (as referred in Article 9). It can be used to purchase phone airtime, internet data packages, and/or online education services paid for educators and/or students as part of the implementation of learning from home program.

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📅 13th April 2020 (national level)

Circular letter number 443/6229 dated 13th April 2020 regarding the rearrangement of educational activities due to COVID-19 pandemic in Yogyakarta. This letter is addressed to all Regents/Mayors in Yogyakarta, Head of Yogyakarta Regional Office of Ministry of Religious Affairs, Head of Dikpora Yogyakarta.

These circular letters follow up the status of the COVID-19 disaster emergency response in Yogyakarta; the circular letter of the Minister of Education and Culture RI number 4 of 2020 concerning the implementation of education policy in emergencies of COVID-19; Governor of Yogyakarta decree number 65/Kep 2020 concerning the statement of COVID-19 emergency disaster response status in Yogyakarta; Governor circular letter number 421/5598 dated 30th March 2020 concerning extension of distance/online learning period for students during COVID-19 emergency in Yogyakarta; results of the evaluation of distance learning of each regional apparatus in the education sector of Yogyakarta and Regency/City. This circular letter rearranges the educational activities including halting the learning activities in schools for TK/RA students since 15th April 2020 to 28th April 2020; the extension of the distance learning online activities for SD/MI, SMP/MTS, SMA/MA, SM/MAK, and SLB students from 15th April–28th April 2020.

📅 13th April 2020 (national level)

One of the efforts in supporting the distance learning programs, the Minister of Education and Culture (Mendikbud) Nadiem Makarim released the 'Learning from Home' program which will be broadcasted by the Television Republik Indonesia (TVRI) during this corona virus pandemic (COVID-19).

The 'learning from home' program is one of the ministry's efforts to support the learning for all people, especially for those who have limited internet access due to the economic condition and geographical location.

'Learning from home' program starts airing on TVRI on Monday, 13th April 2020 at 08:00 WIB', explained Nadiem.

<https://www.beritasatu.com/nasional/618811-pembelajaran-jarak-jauh-mendikbud-rilis-program-belajar-dari-rumah>, 9th April 2020. Accessed on 05/05/2020.

📅 13th April 2020 (Yogyakarta City and Gunungkidul District)

Circular letter of Gunungkidul Regional Office of the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports number: 421/2019/MP-1 concerning extension period Of learning from home (Bdr) during the coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic in the educational units of Gunungkidul.

Extend the period of implementing online learning activities (BDR), learning through TVRI or manual assignments given from teachers for primary school/MI, junior high school/MTs and temporarily stop the learning process of package A program, package B program, package C program, and LKP programs throughout Gunungkidul District from 15th–28th April 2020.

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 13th April 2020 (Yogyakarta City and Gunungkidul District)

Circular letter of Gunungkidul Regional Office of the Ministry of Religious Affairs number B-625/Kk.12.02/1/KP.02.2/05/2020 concerning the extension period of work from home.

The period of work from home for all employees of Gunungkidul Regional Office of the Ministry of Religious Affairs is extended until 29th May 2020 and will be further evaluated as needed.

 21th April 2020 (Yogyakarta Province level)

Circular letter of Yogyakarta Regional Office of the Ministry of Religious Affairs number B-1240.1/KW 12.1/4/HM.01/04/2820 concerning the extension period of work from home and working hours regulations during Ramadhan 1441 H, employees at Yogyakarta Regional Office of the Ministry of Religious Affairs until 13th May 2020.

 21th April 2020 (Yogyakarta City and Gunungkidul District)

Circular letter of the Minister of Religious Affairs number B-570/Kk.12.02/1/KP.0022/04/2020 concerning extension period of work from home and working hours regulations during Ramadhan 1441 H, employees at the Gunungkidul Regional Office of the Ministry of Religious Affairs.

WFH period is extended to 13th May 2020.

 24th April 2020 (Yogyakarta Province level)

Circular letter of the Minister of Religious Affairs number B-1259/Kw.12.2/1/PP.01.1/04/2020 concerning invitation to watch 'Syiar Madrasah' during Ramadhan 1441 H.

Following up on the Letter of Directorate of KSKK Madrasah of the Ministry of Religious Affairs number: 281/Dj.I/Dt.I.I/HM.01/04/2020. The directorate of KSKK Madrasah during of Ramadan will hold an additional education service with the title 'Syiar Madrasah' which will be aired on Metro TV. This program aims to provide character education for madrasah students during Ramadan 1441 H.

 12th May 2020 (Yogyakarta Province level)

Circular letter of the Minister of Religious Affairs number B-1353/kw.12.1/3/KP.01.1/05/2020 concerning the extension period of the implementation of work from home of the employees in the Yogyakarta Regional Office of the Ministry of Religious Affairs.

WFH is extended until 29th May 2020.

Part 10 of 12

 18th May 2020 (national level)

Circular letter number 15 year 2020 concerning guidelines for organising learning from home during the coronavirus disease (COVID-19) emergency, signed on 18th May 2020 by the Secretary General of the Ministry of Education.

One of government's efforts in fulfilling the rights of students to obtain educational services during the coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic is through the organisation of learning from home program. It is stated in the circular letter number 4 year 2020 regarding the implementation of education and emergency policy during the coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic.

The letter regulates the following:

1. Learning from home during the emergency of coronavirus disease (COVID-19) is implemented in accordance with the protocols of COVID-19 management.
2. Learning from home through online and/or offline learning is implemented in accordance with the guideline of the implementation of learning from home as stated in the appendix in this circular letter.

The purpose of learning from home (BDR) program is to ensure the fulfillment of the rights of students to obtain education services during COVID-19 pandemic, to protect the education staffs from the adverse effects of COVID-19, to prevent the transmission of COVID-19 in education units, and to ensure the fulfillment of psychosocial supports for for educators, students, and parents.

 18th May 2020 (Yogyakarta Province level)

Decision of Director General of Islamic Education number 2791 of 2020 concerning guidelines of curriculum in emergency period for Madrasah.

Determine the guidelines of curriculum in the emergency period for Madrasah as stated in the appendix as unseparated parts of the decision.

 27th May 2020 (Yogyakarta City and Gunungkidul District)

Decision of Yogyakarta Governor Number 121/KEP/2020 issued on 27th May 2020 concerning the extension of emergency period of COVID-19 in Yogyakarta, extending the emergency period of COVID-19 from 30th May 2020–30th June 2020. This decision is applicable from 30th May 2020–30th June 2020.

 28th May 2020 (national level)

Circular letter of the Minister of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform number 57 of 2020 concerning changes to the circular letter number 19 concerning adjustment of the ASN work system in an effort to prevent the spread of COVID-19 at government agencies.

Extension of the period of work from home to 4th June 2020.

Part 11 of 12

 28th May 2020 (national level)

Circular letter of the Minister of Religious Affairs of Republic of Indonesia number 14 of 2020 concerning the second amendment to the circular letter of the Ministry of Religious Affairs number 9 of 2020 concerning the adjustment of the work system for Ministry of Religious during the application of the large-scale social restrictions (PSBB).

The determination of the PSBB and the period of work from home is extended until 4th June 2020 and will be further evaluated as needed.

 29th May 2020 (national level)

Circular letter of Minister of State Apparatus Empowerment and Bureaucratic Reform number 58 of 2020 concerning the work system of civil servants in the new normal order.

Adjustment of the work system can be implemented through flexibility in the regulation of the WFO and WFH.

 29th May 2020 (Yogyakarta Province level)

Yogyakarta Governor issued a circular letter number 421/8194 addressed to all regents/mayors in Yogyakarta, Regional office of the ministry of religious affairs, and head of Yogyakarta education office. The circular letter stated the extension period for distance/online learning from 2nd–26th June 2020 to anticipate the transmission of COVID-19. This circular letter is a follow-up for the previous circular letter concerning the extension period of distance learning to 30th June 2020 by considering the high risk of COVID-19 transmission. <https://www.antaraneews.com/berita/1523832/gubernur-diy-perpanjang-kegiatan-belajar-dari-rumah-hingga-26-juni>, Friday 29th May 2020 20:16 WIB.

 29th May 2020 (Yogyakarta Province level)

Circular letter of Regional Office of Education, Youth and Sports number: 421/04690/ concerning learning after Eid holidays 1441 H In Sma, Smk, And Slb in Yogyakarta.

Stated that after Eid holidays, the learning activities will be conducted through online/distance learning from 2nd June 2020–26th June 2020.

And the students will start attending school in the new academic year of 2020/2021 from 13th July 2020.

Part 12 of 12

 28th May 2020 (Yogyakarta City and Gunungkidul District)

Circular letter of Minister of Religious Affairs number B -1451/Kw.12.1/3/KP.01.1/05/2020 concerning the extension of the implementation period of work from home and preparation of the new normal order for all employees in the Yogyakarta regional office of the Ministry of Religious Affairs.

The period of work from home for all employees in the Yogyakarta Regional Office of the Ministry of Religious Affairs is extended to 4th June 2020 and will be further evaluated as needed.

 29th May 2020 (Yogyakarta City and Gunungkidul District)

Circular letter of Minister of Religious Affairs number B-655/Kk.12.02/1/KP.02.2/03/2020 regarding the extension period of the implementation of work from home and preparation of the new normal order for all employees in the regional office of the Ministry of Religious Affairs in Gunungkidul District.

The period of work from home for all employees in the Gunungkidul Regional Office of the Ministry of Religious Affairs is extended to 4th June 2020 and will be further evaluated as needed.

 29th May 2020 (Yogyakarta City and Gunungkidul District)

Circular Letter of Department of Education, Youth, and Sports of Gunungkidul District Number 421/2372/MP-3 concerning extension period of learning from home (Bdr) during the coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic period in education environment in the Gunungkidul District.

Continuing learning from home activities for kindergarten/RA, primary school/MI and junior high school/MTs up to 24th June 2020.

 4th June 2020 (Yogyakarta Province level)

Circular letter of Minister of Religious Affairs number B-1481/Kw.12.1/3/KP.01.1/06/2020 concerning arrangement and adjustment of employee management in the Yogyakarta Regional Office of the Ministry of Religious Affairs.

Starting from 5th June, each work unit should adjust its work system, including:

1. Implementation of official tasks from the office (work from office).
2. Implementation of official duties from home (work from home).

 15th June 2020 (national level)

The Ministry of Education and Culture (Kemendikbud) and the National COVID-19 Task Force, the coordinating Ministry of Human Development and Culture (Kemenko PMK), Ministry of Religious Affairs (Kemenag), Ministry of Health (Kemenkes), Ministry of Home Affairs (Ministry of Home Affairs), National Disaster Management Plan (BNPB), and the House of Representatives Commission X of the Republic of Indonesia announced plans to formulate a joint decree of the four ministries on guidelines for organising learning in the new academic year in the coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic period via a webinar, Monday (15/06).

Minister of Education and Culture (Mendikbud), Nadiem Anwar Makarim said 'The principle of the issuance of educational policies during the COVID-19 pandemic period is to prioritise the health and safety of students, educators, education personnel, families, and the community'.

The new academic year of 2020/2021 for early childhood education (PAUD), basic education, and secondary education will be started in July 2020. However 'For areas in the yellow, orange, and red zones, it is prohibited to do face-to-face learning in education units'. Education units in these zones continue to learn from home.

Annex 3: Stakeholders' voices

'The advantages of Google Classroom in online learning are: easy to learn, simple, available chrome book for learning makes it is more accessible, can be accessed from any places with internet connection. Thus, it can be used for distance learning (PJJ) especially during this period.' (Principal, Yogyakarta City)

'Some applications recommended by the Kemendikbud, such as Ruang Guru, Zenius, and Rumah Belajar, are not used. One of the reasons these applications are not used is that the videos are linked to the Youtube channel. Another reason is that these applications have not been socialised and no trainings provided yet.' (Principal, Gunungkidul)

'Because in this area there are many obstacles, the majority of students come from poor family, far from signal, so we stress the long-distance learning by giving them offline assignment, we didn't use online learning yet.' (Headmaster, Gunungkidul)

'Some use JogjaBelajar. We also have JogjaBelajar. Some others use Google Classroom. It's okay to choose any media, we don't... but we have JogjaBelajar. I think, JogjaBelajar still needs a lot of improvements, but we hope for the better improvement because this is our free product. We don't need to pay but we only need mobile data or internet.' (Provinsi Education Office)

'For Jogjabelajar, based on what the teacher said to me, in my opinion, it might be lacking in substance. The link was sent to school late. However, in terms of materials, they are easy to understand. Maybe it needs more socialisation, so teachers can understand better in using it.' (Principal, Gunungkidul)

'(Jogjabelajar), I wanted to use it, and the students have joined in my class, but not all students understand how to use it. It requires Gmail, should have an email and not all students have an email. That's the first problem. The second, it is almost similar with "Ruang Guru". However, technically it is more complicated. In Ruang Guru, I've had used "Ruang Guru", for example I wanted to create materials or questions, so I had my own question bank under my name. Then, for example my classes were A, B, C, D. When I want to shift I, only need to click once then I can share it to any class I want, either only in class A or all classes. However, in "JogjaBelajar", it's not that easy. When I click class A, I need to retype so does for other classes, you know, it's complicated. Why we need to repeat typing, it's not effective to repeat our works. I hope the features will be improved at least close to "Ruang Guru" which is easier to access. Thus, teachers have their own question bank and can share with one another. There is no need to retype to convey or share.' (Teacher, Yogyakarta City)

'I have tried it (Jogja belajar) once. The students had participated in my class too. But not all students could access the Jogja belajar. It requires an email account to register. We have to have Gmail account while not all my students have email account. That was one issue. Actually, it is basically the same as Ruang Guru but it is more complicated. I have used Ruang Guru before and I think it was very easy to use. I could have my own questions bank and I could distribute it to many classes that I have created. But using Jogja Belajar I could not do the same. I had to

prepare another task all over again if I wanted to distribute it to the different class. So, I think it was troublesome.’ (Teacher, Yogyakarta City)

‘Jogja Belajar was created by Tekomdik. It was initially part of rumah belajar. Not many people use it because the content is not well developed. The learning content in the application was very limited. The last content was updated in 2017 or 2018’ (Teacher, Gunungkidul)

‘Incidentally in this school, we use Geschooll learning application, and it has been used for 4 years, so there are no more pros and cons between parents and school.’ (Teacher, Yogyakarta City)

‘WhatsApp (WhatsApp), one of the familiar media for teachers/students. There is no need to conduct training for using this media as it can be simply accessed using a mobile phone. Generally, WhatsApp is for communication, consultation, and information sharing. Teachers first communicate with students using WhatsApp Group because this is the easiest. Teachers can inform first in WhatsApp Group before sending learning materials or assignments in the Google Classroom, Google Form, for example.’ (Teacher, Gunungkidul)

‘The majority uses WhatsApp since the app is deemed as the most inexpensive app and it is easier to be used as well, like when picture of the assignment needs to be taken and it can be sent directly through the app’. (Teacher, Yogyakarta City)

‘Actually, the City Education Office has recommended a learning tool called online KBS (Student Learning Consultation) since the last 4 years, but the material given is only limited to subject covered in the National Exam and specifically intended for Junior and Senior High School student in Yogyakarta City. The app includes learning material, learning videos, questions, discussion and provide questions and answer facilities. The one who provides the material is the chosen teachers of Yogyakarta City. It is still used by both teachers and students.’ (Principal, Yogyakarta City)

‘The materials provided in Ruang guru and Jogja belajar are not really in line with the school’s curriculum. The materials are too outdated, and the schools’ materials have already advanced.’ (Principal, Yogyakarta City)

‘Teachers need to learn new technology for teaching-learning activities. For instance, attending seminars or workshops to learn how to use new applications. All this time, the the webinars available are only providing theories instead of actual practice.’ (teacher, Yogyakarta City)

‘Review on the ICT subject for students. ICT class has been cancelled. As a matter of fact, ICT subject is the basic knowledge when taking UNBK of computer-based test. I wondered why the ICT class was cancelled. Meanwhile, the current ICT classes do not teach basic knowledge. it is rather on applied programs. So, I think it is better to learn technology from the beginning.’ (Teacher, Yogyakarta City)

‘In the future, because it is not yet possible for students to return to school, the government will facilitate the teachers themselves with a website or portal to support us to teach. not only giving assignments but also transferring knowledge.

The government facilitates us with IT training, inevitably in the future we must understand that this turns out to be a learning for us, it turns out IT is important, if conditions are like this we can't help but have to use IT while if we don't have IT skills we finally surrender, yes surrender monotone of using WhatsApp group. Suggestions for young teachers to join IT training and later to develop free educational applications.' (Teacher, Yogyakarta City)

'There is an increase in household expenses after distance learning, such as electricity usage and airtime purchases. However, there is no purchase for a new mobile phone as the child use his older brother's phone. Airtime purchases before the pandemic was Rp 40,000. Now, it is Rp 65,000. It is not easy to say whether it is burdensome or not. This condition must be accepted and endured especially for the benefit of school children.' (Parents, Yogyakarta City)

Parents feel quite burdened with the purchase of airtime/mobile data for supporting distance learning. 'Quite burdensome, but rather than going to school, (I) feel unsafe.' (Parents, Gunungkidul)

'We used to spend some money to pay the transportation costs, but now the money is used to pay the internet bill. The expenditure for allowance money is also reduced because now we can provide snacks at home. The decrease of expenditure is not really significant. But one thing for sure is that it does not increase. If we used to give allowance money for 50.000 in a week, now we use that money to buy snacks for the children at home.' (Parents, Yogyakarta City)

'For training there are two types, In-house training is usually held in schools, later there will be a special team that provides training to fellow teachers. The last training yesterday was training on using G Suite for Education and filling out e-report cards.' (Teacher, Gunungkidul)

'For learning during PJJ, it varies. Because HR is not the same between the teachers, the school implements it according to the capabilities of the teachers. With the previous training using Google classroom, it is hoped that the teachers can implement it'. (Teacher, Yogyakarta City)

'In its implementation, the school makes a schedule for PJJ phase 1 (before an extension), the school still uses 3 subjects a day. The implementation is exactly like in an ordinary class, even though it is a virtual class using WhatsApp class groups. After the teacher enters and greets students, the teacher shares the link and students enter using Google classroom. Learning is planned to be exactly like ordinary learning, there are preliminary, core and closing activities.' (Teacher, Yogyakarta City)

'She/he (student) has been missing for one month, I can't contact them, then I visit their home, it turns out that their economic condition is poor. If it related to economic condition, we also have no idea what to do'. (Teacher, Yogyakarta City)

'In first grade, all of long-distance learning is accessed through online system. Nevertheless, in the third grade there is offline learning because their parents are poor and their house is near school. Every day, they take the assignments regularly' (Teacher, Yogyakarta City)

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